

METHOD FOR EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE ACUTE TOXICITY OF PLANT COLLECTIONS

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Relevance: Currently, the problems of preserving and strengthening human health are becoming increasingly urgent on a global scale. In particular, the side effects of synthetic chemical drugs, allergic reactions, and negative consequences resulting from long-term use increase the need for natural medicines. From this point of view, the importance of medicines prepared on the basis of medicinal plants in our lives is increasing. Medicinal plants have been used in folk medicine since ancient times and have natural, environmentally friendly properties that have a mild effect on the human body. The modern pharmaceutical industry also pays great attention to the production of effective medicines from the components of medicinal herbs. Therefore, conducting scientific research on the study of medicinal plants, the possibilities of their proper collection, processing, and use as a medicinal product is a pressing issue. The choice of this topic, on the one hand, contributes to the formation of a healthy lifestyle, and on the other hand, serves the preservation and development of our national traditional medicine.

Objective of the study: The purpose of this work is to study the acute toxicity of a mixture made from plantain, snowdrop, mountain ash, and peppermint in experiments.

Methods and techniques: 18 white outbred mice weighing 19-21g were used for the experiment.

For the determination of acute toxicity, a 2% aqueous solution of the collection was prepared. During the experiment, white outbred mice were administered 0.4 ml (400 mg/kg), 0.6 ml (600 mg/kg), and 0.8 ml (800 mg/kg) of the above solution orally. On the first day of the experiment, the animals were observed hourly in laboratory conditions, where external appearance indicators (condition of hair, mucous membranes, etc.); functional state (survival during the experiment, general condition, possible seizures and death) and behavior were recorded. Subsequently, daily, for 2 weeks, under vivarium conditions, the general condition and activity of animals in all groups, peculiarities of behavior, reaction to tactile, pain, sound, and light stimuli, frequency and depth of respiratory movements, heart rate, condition of the hair and skin, tail position, amount and consistency of fecal masses, urine output rate, changes in body weight, and other indicators were observed.

Results: The obtained results showed that the acute toxicity of the studied collection was not observed at 400 mg/kg, 600 mg/kg, 800 mg/kg. In terms of toxic activity, it was found that the harmlessness of our studied pharmacological object is practically non-toxic according to the A.V. Stefanov scale.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that the results of acute toxicity in laboratory animals were not observed at doses 400 mg/kg, 600 mg/kg, 800 mg/kg. It was determined that the harmlessness of the studied pharmacological object in terms of toxic activity is practically non-toxic according to the Stefanova A.V. scale.